

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RECREATIONAL PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND STATE AND TRAIT ANXIETY

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Abstract

Physical activity is associated with better mental health, but the literature does not distinguish which types of activity (e.g. recreational versus other types) are more strongly associated with better mental health. Physical activity has benefits for reducing levels of anxiety. However, factors that affect physical activity participation for individuals with anxiety disorders have not been well studied. Anxiety should be seen as a complex, heterogeneous phenomenon. Spielberger et al. have emphasized that anxiety can be conceptualized in two ways, as a stable disposition and as a transient emotional state that everyone experiences from time to time. Both trait and state anxieties have been conceptualized as unitary constructs. Here, we aimed to clarify the roles of state and trait anxiety in physical activity participation by examining relationships among four major study variables in Latvian adults. Materials and methods, Instruments. Method: 31 Latvian adults (in age 27-58) were evaluated. An exclusion criterion was practicing leisure time physical exercises. Respondents were measured 4 times within 2 years. After excluding from the sample only 17 were used to process the results. State-Trait Anxiety Inventories (STAI-S and STAI-T), (The State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-Y) (Spielberger, Gorsuch, & Lushene, 1970) and check list about recreational physical activities. Results: Changes were evaluated 4 times within 2 years The results do not show statistically significant reduction of

the level of the trait anxiety of STAI-Y ($p < .05$) related to frequency and type of recreational physical activity. Conclusions: there is significantly less research about the effects of physical activity on anxiety. As a consequence, there is not enough evidence to draw conclusive connections between exercise and anxiety is not enough evidence to draw conclusive connections between exercise and anxiety. Limitations: The use of self-rating measures which bears the risk of an under- or overestimation of symptoms.

Keywords: *recreational physical activity, emotions, state anxiety, trait anxiety.*

Introduction

Anxiety – trait anxiety. Anxiety is characterized by excessive worrying, hypervigilance (Wittchen & Hoyer, 2001), and physical symptoms originating due to heightened activation of the sympathetic nervous system (Kong et al., 2022).

Anxiety is becoming the most common mental disorder among various populations worldwide (Booth et al., 2016; Steel et al., 2014). An important conceptual development in the exploration of the phenomenon of anxiety can be attributed to the work of Spielberger (1966). Spielberger defined anxiety as a state characterized by subjective, consciously perceived feelings of tense and apprehension accompanied by arousal of the autonomic nervous system (Spielberger, 1966). Spielberger also has made a distinction between state and trait anxiety. He defined 2 forms of anxiety: state and trait anxiety.

State anxiety is the temporary dimension of anxiety that is related to stress responses, and trait anxiety is the character dimension of anxiety that is related to the long-term stability of personality (Spielberger, 1983).

Anxiety can be a personality trait which implies a predisposition to perceive a wide range of circumstances as threatening and a tendency to respond with excessive apprehension to such situations (Spielberger, 1966). Anxiety as a trait is a personal disposition that characterizes an individual's tendency to perceive situations as threatening and thus to experience anxiety in stressful situations (Gaudry et al., 1975). It is a relatively stable personality trait and a risk factor for the origins of various anxiety-related disorders, depression, and other mental disorders. High trait anxiety causes cognitive control deficit, implicit emotion regulation deficit and risks of emotional disorders (Kong et al., 2022). Besides, high trait anxiety is associated with reduced self-regulatory executive functions and implicit emotion regulation deficits, which may cause emotional and behavioural problems (Liu & Wang, 2018). It is posing a threat to the quality of life, well-being, and could even lead to suicidal tendencies (Abreu et al., 2018). It can

take over all areas of a person's life and cause them to worry about stimuli that are not actually dangerous. Individuals tend to respond with extreme anxiety in everyday situations, but in anxious situations they may experience intense anxiety accompanied by manifestations of autonomic nervous system dystonia (palpitations, dizziness, respiratory changes, gastrointestinal disturbances, fatigue, etc.) (Brants, 2019).

It is possible that an individual who has anxiety as a trait also experiences the tension caused by various frustrations more intensively, thus he is at a higher risk of depression. People with high trait anxiety fail to synchronize default mode network of the brain during resting state (Imperatori, 2019) which means that anxiety as a trait can have far-reaching consequences in a person's daily life. Since the autonomic or voluntary part of the nervous system is involved, it is important that these bodily reactions cannot be controlled by the person's will.

Anxiety as a trait is not directly observed but is expressed as a state of anxiety when stress is experienced (Reiss, 1997).

State anxiety. State anxiety has been defined as an unpleasant emotional response while coping with threatening or dangerous situations (Spielberger, 1983), which includes cognitive appraisal of threat as a precursor for its appearance (Lazarus, 1991). Eysenck and Calvo (1992) argue that state anxiety occurs in threatening situations and is mutually influenced by trait anxiety and situational stress.

Even a low trait anxiety person will experience state anxiety providing a presence of a sufficiently threatening situation. However, trait anxiety tends to moderate the levels of state anxiety, which are provoked by certain situational demands. High trait anxiety individuals can experience more frequent and more intensive state anxiety compared to low trait anxiety individuals; however, they are not anxious all the time. On the other hand, similar short-lived states of anxiety can be found in individuals who don't have a high tendency towards anxious responding. In such cases, experience of state anxiety can be a reaction to certain situational demands (Tovilovic et al., 2009).

The main assumption of the state-trait models is that the effects of traits on behaviour are mediated by states, i.e., that state influence more directly internal processing activities and have a more direct effect on behaviour than trait.

The relationships between anxiety and behaviour outcomes have been described in Spielberger's Cross-Sectional Model of Anxiety. This model proposes that state anxiety causes behavioural reactions directly through defence mechanisms and adaptive processes to avoid stressful situations (Spielberger, 1983; Spielberger, 1966). In addition, trait anxiety directly

influences one's cognitive appraisal, which has an impact on how an individual perceives stressful situations (Spielberger, 1966). This model led to consider that state and trait anxiety may have a profound influence on physical activity behaviour.

Studies on physical activity behavior and its association with anxiety can be highlighted research of Hainaut and Bolmont (2006). Authors of the study point out that state anxiety increases muscle tension, arousal, and thereby focus of attention, which regulates sensory processing. Robazza, Bortoli, and Nougier (1998) studied the relationship between anxiety and performance of members of the Italian national Archery team and concluded that there is a relationship between high anxiety and weak performance.

It has been pointed out (Kroenke et al., 2007) that more research is needed focusing on anxiety, its screening, diagnosis, and treatment.

Physical recreational activity. Physical activity is a broad term relating to any skeletal bodily movement which results in energy expenditure, whereas exercise is an organized subset of physical activity for the goal of improving physical fitness (Caspersen et al., 1985). "Recreational" physical activity means organized or non-organized sport, leisure time physical activities (Zulyniak, 2020). Recreational activities are mainly performed in leisure time and covers sport and exercise activities, cultural activities, outdoor activities, social activities and similar activities with the purpose of bringing pleasure, joy, amusement and meaning to our lives (Pressman et al., 2009). Many studies have investigated terms either 'physical activity' or 'exercise'. Physical activity has been shown empirically great benefits for physical health (Ellye & Arroll, 2002) and psychological functioning (Berger & Owen, 1998; D'Alonzo et al., 2004). Large, cross-sectional analyses have determined significant associations between physical exercise and mental health outcomes.

Physical activity has been shown in a meta-analysis to help reduce levels of anxiety (Pertuzzello et al., 1991; Schuch, 2019) not only by its impact on biological systems, (Goldfarb et al., 1991; Hoffmann, 1997) but also by improving emotional status (Stutts, 2002) especially when exercise gives people relief and time away from daily worries (Breus & O'Connor, 1998).

Healthcare providers increasingly recommend regular physical activity as an appropriate treatment to improve physical and psychological health (Ma et al., 2009; Berger & Owen, 1998). Individuals with anxiety disorders have been shown to have higher levels of state and trait anxiety than the general population (McLean & Woody, 2001; Spano, 2001; Pertuzzello et al., 1991). Studies examining outcomes of recreational running assessed

psychological outcomes such as mood, well-being, affect, cognitive function, self-efficacy, vitality, flow, perceived health, and life satisfaction. Likewise, some studies reported reductions in depression, anxiety, and stress (Pereira, 2021).

Santos (2008) also found anxiety relation with physical activity levels. A group of 200 elderly subjects was divided into two groups of 100, one physically active and the other inactive. It was observed that the inactive individuals obtained higher anxiety scores than their active counterparts. Leisure activities eliminate negative feelings and thoughts and help achieve positive ones (Steptoe et al., 1989). As low force, rhythmic and long-term activities do not force the body and include no risk of turning into a competitive content, participation in sports, social and cultural activities are recommended to cope with anxiety (Bond et al., 2002; Gosselin & Taylor, 1999). Implementation of these activities in groups increases its effectiveness (Cahill & Foa, 2005).

As leisure activities are important in eliminating anxiety, especially exercising supports releasing hormones providing relaxation and so eliminates some negative feelings such as depression and anxiety. The importance of doing leisure activities is highlighted in many resources (Kalyon, 1994; Müftüoğlu, 2005). It is seen that there are studies investigating exam anxiety, state, and trait anxiety (Günay et al., 2008; Kozacıoğlu, 2012) and reporting that socio-cultural and sports activities have an effect on self-esteem and social anxiety (Steptoe et al., 1989; Togo et al., 2006).

Studies show the importance of exercises, sports, and participation in socio-cultural activities in coping with anxiety (Bond et al., 2002; Steptoe et al., 1989) as regular physical activities are supportive in the positive orientation of feelings and behaviors and reduce the level of anxiety. Regular physical activities are stated to be supportive in the positive orientation of feelings and behaviors and reduce the level of anxiety (Müftüoğlu, 2005).

In their study, Ardahan and Lapa (2011) have indicated that individuals participate in outdoor recreational activities to integrate nature, to influence their health positively, to get rid of troubles and stress, to get rid of monotony, to relax, to increase work efficiency, to be with friends, to acquire and use new skills, to get into a new circle, to get rid of loneliness, etc.

A review by Schuch et al. highlighted inconsistencies in exercise treatments (e.g., type and intensity of physical activity), that may be related to the conflicting results in this literature. With these inconsistencies, there is risk that positive aspects of the relationship between physical activity and mental health are being overlooked (Schuch et al., 2017). Looking to anxiety, there is significantly less research about the effects of physical activity on

anxiety. As a consequence, there is not enough evidence to draw conclusive connections between exercise and anxiety (Stonerock et al., 2015). Physical activity is associated with better mental health, but the literature does not distinguish which types of activity (e.g., recreational versus other types) are more strongly associated with better mental health. These findings suggest key questions about the roles of state and trait anxiety as they relate to recreational physical activity in Latvian adult population.

The objective of this study is to measure relationships of physical activity and state and trait anxiety, distinguishing between recreational forms and frequency of physical activity.

Our objective is to clarify the role of state and trait anxiety in physical activity participation of Latvian adults, by examining the relationships among four variables: state anxiety, trait anxiety, frequency of physical activity and form of recreational physical activity.

Materials and methods

This study was composed sample of 31 Latvian adults (8 men and 23 women) in age 27 – 58. An exclusion criterion was practicing leisure time physical exercises.

Respondents were measured 4 times within 2 years. Excluded from the sample were respondents who did not complete at least one assessment test, refused to participate, or did not correctly fill out the questionnaires. As a result, from sample of 31 respondents, only 17 were used to process the results.

Data Collection Procedures. Measurements were taken twice a year – in spring and autumn. All individuals received the same verbal instructions, and any doubts were clarified before the questionnaires were filled out. The instruments also contained written instructions on how to complete them.

Assessment instruments. Data for this study were collected using 3 instruments: the Demographic Inventory (DI), Physical activity checklist, the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory Form Y (STAI-Y).

DI -Demographic data on study subjects included three items: age, sex, education. *Physical activity checklist* included data about habits of physical activities –indoor or outdoor physical activity, type of Physical activity and frequency of Physical activity.

State-Trait Anxiety. – In order to operationalize distinction between state and trait anxiety, Spielberger, Gorsuch and Lushene developed the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI; 1970) (Spielberger, 1983). The Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) has been widely used to measure the state and trait components of anxiety. The STAI-Y is a self-administered questionnaire that measures subjective feelings of state and trait

anxiety. The STAI has been shown to have excellent psychometric properties with good reliability and validity (Barnes et al., 2002). The STAI-Y includes 40 items rated on a 4-point Likert-type scale from 1 (not at all) to 4 (very much). The STAI-Y has two subscales that assess state anxiety (Y1, 20 items) and trait anxiety (Y2, 20 items). In this inventory anxiety was measured by the two self-rated STAI scales (State and Trait Anxiety Inventory). State anxiety, i.e., how one feels now; and Trait anxiety, i.e., how one generally feels. Both scales consist of 20 items. The state scale has 10 reverse-scored items, the trait scale has 7. The state scale (STAI-S) requires individuals to express how they feel “at the moment” in relation to the 20 items contained on a 4-point Likert scale (not at all – 1; somewhat – 2; moderately so – 3; very much so – 4). The trait scale (STAI-T) also has 20 items, but individuals are instructed to respond how they “generally feel” on a different 4-point Likert scale (almost never – 1; sometimes – 2; often – 3; almost always – 4). Total STAI-Y scores can range from 40 to 160, with higher scores indicating higher anxiety. The score of each scale can vary from 20 to 80 points, with scores below 30 indicating a low degree of anxiety, 31 – 49 a medium level and 50 or more a high degree.

The questionnaire can measure anxiety both in healthy and in clinical populations (Oei et al., 1990). It can be used to test anxiety in various special subgroups and several health conditions. A large body of previous evidence (Booth et al., 2016; Julian, 2011;) have shown the utility and validity of the STAI scales. It is often used in behavioural as well as physiological studies such as skin conductance (Kasos et al., 2018).

The internal validity factor (Cronbach's alpha) in the original study is 0.89 to 0.96 (Spielberger et al., 1983). English Spielberger's Anxiety Test adapted in Latvian version (Škuškovnika, 2004), obtaining the internal validity coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) 0.83 – 0.91 and the average values in subscales in different age and gender groups from 36.60 ± 7.09 to 43.00 ± 9.11 .

Statistical Analysis. As the first step of the *item selection*, we removed reverse-scored state (numbers 1, 2, 5, 8, 10, 11, 15, 16, 19, 20) and trait (numbers 21, 26, 27, 30, 33, 36, 39) STAI items, as the before mentioned findings pointed out the confounding nature of the reverse-scored items (Andras et al., 2020).

The data were analysed using the R Studio statistical package (R Core Team, 2013).

The sample was characterized using descriptive statistics, namely mean and dispersion (standard deviation) measures. The Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests were used to verify sample normality and homogeneity of variances, respectively. Pearson's product-moment correlation was applied to

determine the association between PA and the parameters of anxiety state and trait. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

First, the relationships between STAY-1 and STAY-2 were measured each time. A total – four times. Pearson's product-moment correlation had determined the coefficient correlation and significant correlation of State and Trait among Latvian adults. There is a close correlation in all four measurements between STAI Y-1 and STAIY. In all four cases $p < 0.001$.

Figure 1. State Anxiety correlation with Trait Anxiety

Descriptive statistics examined the mean and standard deviation which State ($M=34.83$ $SD=7.402$) and Trait ($M=37.45$, $SD=7.525$). The scores of each scale indicating a medium level of State-Trait Anxiety (31-49).

The findings are consistent with the with theoretical support for the Spieberger`s construct of anxiety and this was demonstrated by high correlations between Anxiety-State and Anxiety-Trait scales in the subsamples (Vitasari et al., 2011; Novy et al., 1993). The data obtained in the

study do not indicate relationship between type of recreational physical activities (indoor or outdoor recreational physical activity) and frequency of physical activity ($p > 0,05$).

Discussion

The Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) is the most frequently used measure of state and trait non-disorder-specific anxiety (Spielberger, 1970; Manzoni et al., 2008). State anxiety is the temporary dimension of anxiety that is related to stress responses, and trait anxiety is the character dimension of anxiety that is related to the long-term stability of personality (Spielberger, 1989).

Pearson correlations had determined the coefficient correlation and significant correlation of State and Trait among participants. The results showed significant correlation with $p = .000$ ($p < .05$). A similar trend between anxiety as a State and as a Trait has been observed in other studies (Vitasari et al., 2011). The two subscales have been shown to have satisfactory reliability and validity (Spielberger, 1970), which is also confirmed by this study.

This study data does not support the theoretical findings that state, and trait anxiety may have a profound influence on physical activity behaviour and that the inactive individuals obtained higher anxiety scores than their active counterparts (Steptoe et al., 1989).

The data obtained rather confirm findings by Schuch et al. that highlighted inconsistencies in exercise treatments (e.g., type and intensity of physical activity), that may be related to the conflicting results in this literature. With these inconsistencies, there is risk that positive aspects of the relationship between physical activity and mental health are being overlooked (Schuch et al., 2017).

Conclusions

The result of this research supports the main assumption of the state-trait models is that the effects of traits on behaviour are mediated by states, i.e., that state influence more directly internal processing activities and have a more direct effect on behaviour than trait.

If anxiety as a personality trait implies a behavioural disposition that encourages an individual to perceive a broad, objectively safe set of objects as threatening and react more intensely than is objectively necessary (Spielberger et al., 1972), then a statistically significant decrease in anxiety will change both individual behaviours. It will be more adequate in a particular situation and the individual's emotional state.

However, research shows that not only high but also very low levels of anxiety hinder the achievement of high scores, such as in sports (Jones,

1995) or exam (Hancock, 2001). Which leads to the conclusion that an individual's reaction to an anxiety situation is individual. It is possible that anxiety affects the behaviour of everyone in different ways – one starts playing sports more, another directly – less. This study does not show an association between the variables Anxiety as a condition and feature and the type and frequency of physical activity.

Looking to anxiety, there is still significantly less research about the effects of physical activity on anxiety. Therefore, there is not enough evidence to draw conclusive connections between physical activities and anxiety.

Study limitations the generalizability of our results has some limitations. First, the data were collected from Latvian adults, aged 20 – 60 years. Thus, our results may not be applicable to people younger than 20 or older than 60 years, living in other countries with different cultures, or with other mental diseases or disorders. Second, the information was obtained from questionnaires and interviews, which may have bias related to memory capacity, personal influences or opinions, and social desirability. Third, subjects were recruited by voluntary sampling. Thus, outcomes cannot be generalized for individuals diagnosed with anxiety disorders who did not participate or who were attending other clinics. Fourth, this study is limited by using a cross-sectional design to explore relationships between State and Trait anxiety and recreational physical activity. There is still lack of autonomic nervous evidence which implies the psychophysiological response of the body of populations to stressors. Therefore, it is meaningful to design a paradigm for analysing autonomic nervous system (ANS) patterns of State and Trait anxiety by using machine learning methods.

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